

Mapping of Multimedia Communication at the University of Kinshasa

Godfrey BENTH NGOYI¹ and Carlin MBUNDANI WATALU²

Abstract :- This article sets out to provide an overview of the counterpart knowledges in the digital era, in the information and communication sciences teaching programs in our country. This, we are going to talk about the subjects and axes in the program of this sector, which in itself suffers from its popularization among students who are specializing in Information and Communication Sciences at Unikin. This description is more relevant to students who have opted for digital communication, currently known as "Multimedia".

Keywords:- Communication, Media, New media, Digital, Multimedia.

I. INTRODUCTION

Information and Communication Sciences are the latest scientific disciplines to be published. They are by their specificity interdisciplinary in the plural, from where a great debate is engaged between schools that do not understand that they must remain so, given the plurality of disciplines that the Sciences of Information and Communication encompass. The plurality of exogenous methods and theories constitutes a headache for those who claim to minimize this new discipline. But the Information and Communication Sciences have an epistemological status with their own object of study, their own methods and borrowings, and their own theories and paradigms.

The advent of the Internet has made it possible for communication and information to be equipped with new technologies that are essential to their development. This is why we speak more of The New Information and

Communication Technology (NICT). The Internet has facilitated the emergence of new methods of communication in human society. Therefore, the reform at the level of the institutions that organize the Sciences of Information and Communication should actually undergo the contribution of the masters to train executives capable of providing solutions adapted to the new digital realities. This is the reason for the existence (creation) of the option "Multimedia Edition" for some and the faculty for others.

Apart from the introduction and conclusion, the study is divided into three parts: clarification of the concepts, the main lines of the multimedia and a survey of students at the University of Kinshasa.

II. CLARIFICATION OF KEY CONCEPTS

A. Multimedia

In his book entitled "Science, Multimedia, Archives, Publicity and Official Gazette", Bobutaka Bob defines "Multimedia as a branch of ICT that has acquired the status of a scientific discipline using three elements: text, sound and image, whether animated or fixed. An interactive platform that simultaneously performs bibliological, informatics and net-economic functions. Further on, he speaks in a derived sense to encompass software, hardware and interactive editorial content implementing still or animated image, sound, text and hypertext". (B. Bobutaka, 2019:133).

We can summarize its description in a diagram that we were able to draw a more :

Fig. 1: Diagram of the knowledge of Multimedia
 Source: diagram designed by us based on Bobutaka's diagram

The multimedia elements always come from resources that are independent of the HTML document. HTML documents contain hyperlinks to multimedia resources, which may be scattered across the Internet. The linked multimedia elements are automatically transferred to present a web page. Only the use of images and small animations is standardized. The support of sound, video, three-dimensional spaces or other multimedia elements is still based on non-standardized technologies.

Many web browsers offer the possibility to add software (plugins) to extend their functionality, including support for non-standard media types. Streams (audio, video) require a different communication protocol than HTTP. This is one of the reasons why this type of resource often requires a plugin and is poorly integrated into web pages.

We do not want to get lost in the understanding of the concept of Multimedia, but in this article we will talk about Multimedia as an Option/faculty of Information and Communication Sciences. It is the set of teachings oriented to digital communication. Emanation of the computer science, the Multimedia makes use of this last one to manage to answer current needs of communication that they are communicators or communicologists.

Poorly known, Multimedia is apprehended as an option/faculty of photographers, video editors, or cameramen. This lack of knowledge is even evident among students, most of whom are in the first year of a Bachelor's degree program (equivalent to a Master's degree in the LMD system).

Therefore, before returning to the outcomes of multimedia, we will describe in the second point of this study the different subjects in the program of this option/faculty.

B. New media

According to Pierre Trudel, new media are forms of computer media that depend on the redistribution of computers through the Internet with its various services (P. Trudel, 2008: 103).

What we call "new media" are new tools or a new method of distribution made possible by the arrangement of texts, photos and videos circulating through various web platforms, also known as "Multimedia". These tools could very well have evolved without necessarily mentioning new media. It is simply a matter of expanding journalism, photography, audio or video to new platforms.

If we now speak of "new media", it is because we are witnessing a paradigm shift, we are traveling through unexplored media territories, different from the old world, from the "old media". These are new places and new spaces to invest. Somewhat hyperbolically, one could say that the new media are to the information world what America was at that time: a virgin territory, where for an enterprising few, anything seems possible.

It is on this promise that the new media as we know them today were built. Towards the end of the last century, the Internet offered a host of ways to bypass the old media world. These new spaces were made possible in particular by the creation in common of new software having the sharing but also the hackings which consist in breaking the chains imposed by the empires of the Old world. This is how a whole cohort of connected citizens was able to create videos, audio, photos in order to put them online via blogs or websites, to erect, little by little, what was called the new media.

The notion of the new media qualifies works calling upon information technologies in their process of realization or as support of creation (video, data processing, etc). "To transmit data" being the characteristic of any work of art; it is logically that these new technologies could become a territory to invest for the artists. They have two characteristics which interest particularly the artistic field, "the capacity to record this real in the duration and the capacity to modify it".

According to the theorist Lev Manovitch, "the new media are certainly the works realized on digital support (tapes, video and sound, CD-RM, hard disk, Internet site), but also those stemming from old media as the cinema converted to the digital supports for the need of the diffusion" (L. Manovitch, 2001: 105).

Let's remember that new media generally use the Internet and other computer means. In order to understand them, we need to understand the notions related to webcasting such as:

➤ Web radio

"The broadcasting of radio on the Internet has disrupted the usual codes of this medium while opening it up to a new type of listener. This passage from the "airwaves to the networks" has enabled listeners to leave the dependence on the flow and move towards an à la carte radio with more

autonomy in the choice of programs thanks to podcasts and more individualization of programs" (www.wikipedia.org/webradio).

We can therefore talk about a connection media and no longer a reception media. There are multiple inputs: streams, podcasts, rebroadcasts. The listener will therefore look for what interests him or her and is no longer necessarily focused on regular listening to programs. "Nevertheless, listening to live broadcasts remains the preferred option. This shift from mass media to mass media implies a more refined analysis of the information received and requires the development of a critical sense" (www.maisondelaradio.fr).

"The first benefit is obviously the control of the moment of consultation and the possibility of re-listening. The listener is no longer dependent on a schedule and a programming grid. The stream is stored and accessible at will. This is what makes podcasting so successful. The absence of a schedule allows a variation of formats, the program no longer being imprisoned in a fixed duration and adapting to the complexity of the subject matter (podcasted programs sometimes offer long versions, even unedited).

But beyond this first use, a sort of circumstance, a more profound innovation is in the making: web and radio are potentially two types of listening that cohabit, that follow each other, one inscribing itself in the temporal flow, the other allowing to break it to directly access a part or to come back to another already heard. We thus preserve the lightness of assimilation brought by the flow and add to it the possibilities of a direct delinearized access.

"Web radio is therefore the promise of the assets of radio (linearity, listening and mobility), combined with those of the Web (mass of information, reading time), it is the marriage of synchronous and asynchronous. But it is also the risk of the worst of both worlds: the prison of flow and the incommensurability of space. It is therefore above all an opportunity to re-interrogate radio and hypermedia in order to invent new ways of reading and writing, of accessing information, and perhaps of teaching.

Regarding the live or on-demand broadcasting, the web radio broadcasts programs made live or it rebroadcasts pre-recorded programs, because we can't control the flow if we start at different times, we won't have the same audio data.

➤ Web Tv

The term Web TV refers to television channels that broadcast exclusively over the Internet, in contrast to traditional television channels that may broadcast live on the Web or catchup in addition to other broadcast modes (cable, IPTV, satellite), (Martin Michel, 2005: 39).

A Web TV uses *streaming* technology or progressive download to deliver its content on the Web. Clients (users) call up a video stream and watch it from their browser or from a media player.

The video is compressed, converted to a specific codec, and if necessary placed in a container format. It is then sent by server software to clients. Peer-to-peer

exchange models like Joost appeared briefly, but were not successful.

Web TV technology is to be distinguished from IPTV, a technique for broadcasting traditional television via ADSL. IPTV has a reserved bandwidth for its transmission which guarantees the quality of the service to the user, Web TV also uses the transmission by Internet but without reserved or priority bandwidth.

Web TVs have literally developed on the Internet. With the strong development of the consultation of television on mobiles (smartphones, tablets...). The local TV channels have also appropriated this means of broadcasting. The so-called "classic" channels (terrestrial, DTT or cable) are also interested in this means of broadcasting by creating *replay* platforms.

➤ *Social Web*

Social networks, if we are to believe Lino Pungi, refer to a vision of the Internet as a space for socialization, a place where one of its main functions is to make users interact with each other to ensure continuous content production, content, not just the distribution of documents anymore. (Lino Pungi, 2016: 57).

A social network is therefore a set of relationships between a set of relationships between a set of actors. This set can be organized (like a company) or unorganized (like a network of friends) and these relationships can be of a very diverse nature (power, gift exchange, advice, etc.), specialized or not (Michel Forse, 2008: 10). The actors are usually individuals, but they can also be households, associations, etc.

For Lemieux, a social network is a collection of social identities, such as individuals or social organizations, linked together by links created during social interaction (Vincent Lemieux, 2011: 12). Social networks can be formed naturally, such as families, clans, or by affinity (as in some sense, friendships, romantic relationships, etc.), or circumstantially, such as study groups in a classroom. Note that social networks can have conscious or unconscious purposes.

A social network represents a social structure modeled by vertices or nodes and breakpoints (arrows). Vertices or nodes typically refer to people and/or organizations linked by social interactions. Social interactions are represented by arrows.

Talking about the Digital Social Network, "it is an Internet application that gathers profiles, messages, forums, etc., help create a circle of friends, find business partners, work or other people(www.leszed.ed-productions.com). A virtual or real place where you can discuss any topic, exchange images, information; talk about what we love, what we hate; give our opinion on various topics and share our opinions, personal news, interests.

These types of Internet applications, virtual interaction environments or sites dedicated to communicating with acquaintances, meeting new people or building a

professional network, all have the same operation: you create your profile (personal information, photo, interests) by registering online on the site and you invite your friends to join you.

Thereafter, each member can either join an existing group or create his own community with which he will share interests and motivations related to the site, through a system of invitations and search for individual members of the community. Each contact who accepts an invitation increases your network of new contacts. Newcomers take turns registering their contacts, etc., then the site offers applications to encourage members to be active and not just use the virtual site.

A social network responds to the primary need of every individual to belong. In addition to this need to belong, every individual needs to be valued by the other members of his community. Applications are then proposed by the site to encourage members to be active and not only use the site as a showcase. A remark must be made concerning the modalities of registration to the site. Indeed, any member of the network can freely register in the groups or communities he wants without any restriction of number.

Social networks are increasing every day, but the must-haves are: Facebook, Twitter, Flickr, LinkedIn, YouTube, Whatsapp, Viadeo, Myspace, Friendfeed and others.

C. *Digital Communication*

➤ *Definition and concepts*

Digital media refers to various digital media that can bring visibility to a company or organization. This includes a website, social networks, newsletters and also influencer marketing" (www.junior-entreprises.com).

According to Oualidi Habib, digital media is defined as a new discipline of communication but also a field of marketing. The term refers to all actions (communication and marketing) aimed at promoting products and services through a traditional or digital media, aimed at reaching consumers in a personal way. Personal, extremely targeted and interactive. Therefore, the new goal of companies is to target consumers not only on the web but also on all digital media (Oualidi Habib, 2013: 26).

Digital communication is therefore the strategy through which communication actions are carried out on the web, social media and mobile devices. "The question today, for a company, is therefore no longer whether it should be on the Internet but rather how it should position itself there and the strategy it should adopt in order to effectively link traditional media and digital media. Digital communication is a conversational medium" (Oualidi Habib, 2013: 30).

The digital media consumer is very different from the simple passive viewer. He is active, that's why it is important to make him act so that he is more receptive and attentive to messages. In the professional field, digital communication defines communication strategies and actions carried out on the web to convey messages, values or

results that will attract the attention of target Internet users and improve company visibility.

➤ *Objectives of digital media*

Before launching on the Web and social networks, it is essential to define the objectives of digital communication. "Without an objective, without a target to reach, it is difficult to know what path to take and what means to

implement. Concretely, objectives allow you to select the best tools (social networks, online advertising, SMS campaign, etc.) to reach your targets" (Claire Gayet and Xavier Marie, 2016: 66).

The final objective being generally the increase of sales, it is a question of seeing how the notoriety, the image or the loyalty contribute to this increase thanks to digital.

Table 1: Objectives of digital media

N°	Objectives	Definitions	Digital solutions
01.	Notoriety	To be known, to be remembered by the customers	Mass media: YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram...
02.	Image	Build your brand image	Diversity of content and creativity: videos, photos, blogs...
03.	Traffic	Increase traffic on your website	Opportunities to link to a website: advertising, social media...
04.	Acquisition	Recruiting new customers	Easier to reach new targets: online communities, data collection, multiplication of contact points (e-mail, SMS, social networks...).
05.	Transformation, conversion	Encourage visitors to a site to perform an action (purchase, registration, etc.)	Analysis of the customer journey on the site, enhancement of content, simplification of processes.
06.	Loyalty	Build customer loyalty, keep them coming back and buying	Better knowledge of customers and their habits, segmentation of data and media, better follow-up with CRM (Customer Relationship Management).
07.	Research and development	Improve its products and customer knowledge, launch new products.	Monitoring listening, analysis of opinions and comments, co-creation, creation of brand communities.

After defining the key concepts of our study, in the following point, we will address the different axes of the multimedia training program. We talk about the subjects in the program, as well as the related professions.

III. THE MAIN AXES OF MULTIMEDIA

A. *Subjects in the Multimedia program of the University of Kinshasa*

Taken in two years of study, the courses in multimedia are as follows:

➤ *In the first year of Multimedia:*

- English: This course has content related to communication and its daily practices. It is a combination course with other CIS options and allows students to open up to the world of business and work outside our borders;
- Multimedia Integration: here, the subjects allow learners to use multimedia objects in communication via the Internet. This course opens the doors to web programming (tag-based programming) and the design of visuals for digital communication, not to mention the use of storytelling;
- Information and Computer Assisted Presentation (Pre-CAP): This is a course that allows students to design slide shows and cultivate some public speaking skills in their public presentations. The basic software is MS PowerPoint;
- Current Events Seminar: This is a capstone course with other electives that pushes students to immerse themselves in current media events. Papers are presented and defended in a public discussion.

- Information Analysis: this course is dedicated to an in-depth analysis of information using classical methods of content analysis for political and scientific speeches, press articles etc.
- Introduction to programming: this is a course that trains on the design and programming of mobile applications. It prepares students for communication practices for mobile users. The language studied is Visual Basic Studio ;
- Communication Semiology: This is an overview course with other CIS options. This important course allows students to master the notions of meaning, message meaning and especially connotation and denotation of visual communication for businesses;
- Computer Graphics and Iconic Language Analysis: Often misunderstood with reductionist content, this course goes beyond Photoshop. It focuses on the design of graphic information, and the graphic charter with its elements such as logo, typography, colors, images, etc. It is not only practical, but touches on the acts of iconic language, semantics and also the critical analysis of visual identity;
- Computer Science: In the first year, this course is based on the design of relational databases. The students called to the conservation and archiving of the data on computer, are equipped with the appropriate data-processing methods to leave the conceptual model of the data and treatment to the logical model while passing by that organizational and physical of the data and treatments. This course should also provide notions on algorithms and methods of computer analysis.

- Research Methods in CIS: This is a comprehensive course that provides students with the different methods that can help them develop their final work. It teaches endogenous and exogenous methods in Information and Communication Sciences;
 - Classical and computerized documentary techniques: this course gives the notions and practices on the document, documentary institutions, methods of classification, conservation and use of documents. It also uses computer tools for optimal management;
 - General Library and Archival Studies: This course provides students with a general understanding of libraries, archives, and their treatment, preservation and use;
 - Network and client-servers: this course provides notions on computer networks, hardware or architecture, web search, internet and intranet in a company;
 - New Media: This course is very important for all first year undergraduates and is one of the points in our article to understand digital communication. It teaches the notions on the internet and computer networks, the applications of the internet, webcasting with its elements such as web radio, web Tv and social web, the applications of ICT and even the development of computer networks (Lino Pungi 2016:4-7).
- *In the second year, let's say the final year in Multimedia, we have the following courses:*
- Project development and evaluation: we learn how to develop and evaluate projects. These projects are usually the foundation for the development of our respective communities. This is a course for all senior classes in ICT;
 - ICT and Multimedia: this course allows Multimedia students to know the relationship between multimedia and information and communication sciences. It shows the place that the multimedia occupies in the evolution of the ICT;
 - Editing and Bibliology: This course allows you to understand the importance of directories in CIS. Students understand the quintessence of ICT by discovering the mathematical formula that summarizes Information and Communication Sciences, namely $ICT=SI+SC+SM$ (Information Science, Communication Science and Media Science). Also, the writings (MM) are epistemological objects of the Bibliology. Writings understood here as (text, sound and images).
 - The English course: this course in the final year prepares the student to face the professional world, as the English language is a major asset in communication both within the company and between states.
 - The New Paradigms of Communication: it is a subject that accompanies the changeover to New Information and Communication Technologies. These models explain the development of a discipline that has to new arrangements. They are paradigms such as interactivity, linear, circular and hyper-textuality;
 - Management Seminar: It is a course where students get subjects to rely on the direction, management and supervision of a company. It is a practical course taken with other ICT options;
 - Telecommunications Law and Economics: this course provides information on telecommunications legislation;
 - Computer Industry: This course helps students learn more about the computer industry with its innovations and related technologies. From 2D to augmented reality, passing through 3D, we also talk about Artificial Intelligence (AI);
 - Audiovisual and digital editing seminar: this course gives practical tools on editing, because in multimedia, the assembly of three elements (text, sound and image) is recurrent. The software of the Adobe family is more used;
 - Cognitive psychology: it is a subject that opens the students to the understanding of the communication process that starts from our cognition to the materiality ;
 - Theories of marketing: this is a course taken together with the L1 CO (Communication of Organizations) students on the market of products and services. How to position the latter by using the 4Ps of the marketing mix;
 - Project Writing: this hands-on course allows students to write a project following the necessary steps learned in the first year;
 - Intellectual Property Law and Commercial Law: it is a course that gives notions of intellectual property of works, inventions and products, especially in the era of the commonplace wanted by the Internet;
 - Management of a Multimedia Agency: this is a great course that allows the finalists in multimedia to edit, broadcast and distribute content via digital platforms. This course opens the door to the implementation of projects to create a multimedia agency;
- B. Multimedia or digital professions* (www.youtube.com/metiersdumultimedia)
- Many people often wonder what to do after a multimedia training. In addition to the traditional professions known in ICT, such as journalism, communication, etc., there are others that do not replace the old ones, but open new horizons. Here are others that do not replace the old ones, but open new horizons. The different professions linked to digital technology are :
- Computer engineer,
 - Network Analyst,
 - Junior Sales Engineer,
 - The solution architects,
 - Developers in IT support and management of technological solutions for online clients, etc.
- But the top jobs for those who do Multimedia are:
- *Digital Brand Content Manager:*
- It is a job that consists in the valuation of a brand or a company on the internet and on social networks he is responsible for the digital notoriety and its reputation. He is also responsible for the elaboration of the strategic plan of the digital image as well as the follow-up of its strategy. This brand manager manages more than a product or a range of products. He/she makes sure that these different products correspond to the identity, the personality and the values of the brand.

Clearly, we can find different missions for this job:

- Animate brand discourses on social media,
- Optimize brand awareness and acquire traffic,
- Lead and manage web projects in coordination with the different teams,
- Manage digital crisis devices,
- Measure and develop the performance of the actions,
- Participate in the implementation of the relationship marketing program.

➤ *Mobile Web Developer:*

Create computer programs specifically dedicated to the mobile environment, such as smartphones, websites and video games. His first mission is to analyze the needs of his clients, then to ensure the proper functioning of his work and act in case of technical problems. He is at the same time, creator, technician, artist, decision-maker or even analyst, in short an expert of the mobile web mode. He works in close collaboration with designers, project managers and even graphic designers. This means that he has to be a team player.

➤ *Traffic Manager:*

It is a job not very well known. He is an expert in traffic management which allows to increase the visibility of the website, to acquire contacts, but especially to increase the sales of the company. It makes the website profitable.

Its missions are:

- Imagine and implement advertising campaigns on the Internet,
- It must track results by scrutinizing user clicks (time spent on the web page, words indexed by its users in the search engine, etc.),
- As a web marketing professional, he is an expert in SEO, emailing, display and price comparison.

➤ *The Data Protection Officer:*

He is in charge of the security of the company's data. With computerized data protection devices, he ensures the compliance of the company's data, that is to say that he ensures the legal use of the data collected by the company for which he works.

Its missions are:

- Adjust to new regulatory standards related to digital evolution,
- He must assure his customers that their data is in order and that he uses it only for commercial purposes,
- He must know all the laws, rules and regulations regarding data protection.

➤ *Ux Designer*

He is the one in charge of the user experience on a web platform. His main mission is to optimize the online platform of a brand, taking into account the needs of users essentially. He will determine the criteria for users and improve the user interface. To do this, he will conduct studies among them to know what blocks and identify what needs to be improved on the web platform.

Thus:

- It works on visibility,
- It improves the ease of use,
- It facilitates the user's confidence. (5/5 *****).

➤ *Social Media Manager:*

He watches over the e-reputation of an entity (company) via the internet and social networks. He therefore has a role from a strategic point of view. He is not a simple executor, but he defines the strategy with the company's management.

- It identifies the targets and their needs,
- Define an editorial line,
- It selects social platforms on which the company must be present,
- It analyzes the current positioning of the company on the web and on social networks.

Based on his strategy, he sets up a " Social media planning " to :

- Optimize referencing,
- Identify and retain influential bloggers,
- Publish content,
- Build customer loyalty.

It also follows the evolution and results of its different actions with the help of webanalytics, audience measurement and statistics measurement tools (Google Analytics, etc.).

➤ *Architect Big Data:*

Every day, data is generated all over the world. This data can be used by the company to understand customers, guide their decisions and have a competitive advantage over competitors. And to be used, data must be collected and organized, which is the role of the Big Data Architect. He is in charge of collecting raw data that is more or less structured and in large quantities coming from different sources, either internal or external to the company. On a daily basis, he/she organizes the storage of the data, the handling and the restitution of the processed data.

The skills in this area, you need:

- Master Big Data technologies,
- Master the tools and the computer language,
- Be organized and rigorous while resisting stress.

➤ *Data Analyst:*

He or she is in charge of using the information gathered through various channels to facilitate decision-making at the management level. His/her mission consists of processing customer, product and product performance data to identify useful metrics for decision makers. The information provided allows decisionmakers to determine the products to offer customers according to their needs, the marketing strategies to be adopted or the improvements to be made in the production process.

➤ *In charge of web referencing*

His mission is to do everything possible to ensure that his company's website is at the top of the internet search. The audience of a website depends essentially on its quality of its referencing on the search engine. When you type a

keyword, the site at the top of the list will be visited than the one that arrives further in the pages of the search engine.

The referencing is calculated and organized by the referencing manager who identifies the target, competitors and keywords; he also evaluates the algorithms of the search engines by adapting the practices of the company according to the algorithmic changes and the results obtained.

It must therefore fulfill 3 qualities:

- Analyze,
- Organize,
- Adapt.

➤ *The Digital Project Manager:*

The biggest job in the digital world, as it leads a team composed of developers, graphic designers, webmasters, editors, social media managers, etc.

He is in charge of managing a large digital project. He will therefore:

- Drawing up specifications,
- Establish the technical specifics of the project,
- Validate the editorial line,
- Develop the schedule and budget by estimating the time and means for each phase of the project.

His work is not limited to the realization of the project, but he also follows up the good functioning of the project according to the fixed objectives. To be a digital project manager, you need to be able to lead a team and master all the digital disciplines.

We have listed a few multimedia (digital) professions to allow readers to understand the dimension of this option/faculty in information and communication sciences. Note that apart from these professions, there are many others that we cannot mention here, as they are already known by the majority.

IV. METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS OF THE SURVEY

The survey on the program and outlets of multimedia communication proceeds by the method of collecting information, the survey by questionnaire (J-M. De Ketele and X. Roegiers, 1996: 31).

A. *Participants*

The project was carried out in two phases: a first survey conducted in 2020 in the Faculty of Humanities of the University of Kinshasa. During phase 1, a 6-question questionnaire was submitted to a sample of 45 G3 SIC students.

The second phase therefore consisted of a specific survey of assistant candidates in the ICT department. A representative sample of 5. After matching the phase 1 and phase 2 files on knowledge of the multimedia program and opportunities, the final sample is 50 respondents.

B. *Data collection*

The questionnaire consists of six questions:

- The identity of the respondent: in this first part, we determined the age range of the respondents, which varies between 20 and 40 years. We also determined the category of the respondents, having on the one hand students (G3) and on the other hand assistant candidates of the CIS department.
- Questions related to the subject under review: 3 questions were submitted to these two categories of respondents:
 - ✓ Can you choose the multimedia option? (To students) justify your answer.
 - ✓ Why did you choose this option? (To assistant candidates)
 - ✓ What are the opportunities for training in multimedia (All)
 - ✓ How do you rate the current multimedia training program? (All).

C. *Results*

At the University of Kinshasa, the multimedia option of the Department of Information and Communication Sciences is not well known by the students in terms of content and opportunities of multimedia. Out of a total of 45 students, i.e., 100% of the students, only 9 students, i.e., 20%, say yes to the choice of multimedia when they graduate. And 36, or 80% of the respondents do not know the opportunities of the multimedia training, hence they said no.

And out of the 5 candidate assistants interviewed, that is 100% of the candidate assistants, 2 respondents, that is only 40%, justify their choice of multimedia, to face the challenges of digital communication and especially to be useful for the Congolese society and organizations that must face the challenges of digital. And 3, or 60% of the interviewed assistant candidates regret having chosen multimedia, accusing the lack of rigor in the respect of the program, with courses that are given by assistants and supervisors coming mostly from the Faculty of Science.

4 out of 5 candidates, i.e. 80% of the assistants, do not fully know the jobs reserved for those who follow this university training, from which some become photographer's shooters, other image editors in various television channels of the place. Only one candidate listed jobs or opportunities in multimedia.

D. *Discussion*

The data collected from our survey participants can be interpreted as follows:

- The multimedia communication organized at the University of Kinshasa is little chosen by the students who do Information and Communication Sciences. This is due to the lesser popularization of the program of the courses followed and especially on the jobs of those who do this option;
- The precariousness of the digital faculty means that those who do follow multimedia are either discouraged and as a result give it a bad rap with undergraduates;

- Despite the current issues and challenges of digital culture, few students do not know how to reconcile multimedia training with the social realities of the provincial city of Kinshasa.

E. Contribution

Within the framework of this study that we had carried out, it is incumbent upon us to make some proposals/suggestions to students and to those in charge of the faculty in general, and those of the department in particular:

- Organize communication sessions on the merits of choosing multimedia as an option, because currently, economies are dominated by the digital and entrepreneurship 'opens to homo numericus;
- Strengthen the staff in digital communication and especially make the courses that have a mathematical and computer bias more flexible;
- Recruit assistants in the field to facilitate the supervision of young people who choose this option;
- To provide information on the opportunities in multimedia communication as presented in this article of the different digital professions.

V. CONCLUSION

This article has allowed us to understand not only the stakes of the teaching in multimedia, which is an important option in the Information and Communication Sciences field, but also to detect the purposes or professions of the multimedia that the training program of the digitalists pursues.

We first elucidated key concepts of our study, then detailed the subjects that are in the training program in order to stimulate students to follow this training program that meets the current needs in a digital culture.

We also applaud the idea behind the new LMD system (Bachelor - Master - Doctorate) in our country. With the restructuring, Multimedia will now start from the first year, which will open more horizons to new researchers in the field of digital communication.

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